

Kinetics of alkaline hydrolysis of hydroxamic acid in mixed micelles of binary surfactant systems

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The alkaline hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid has been studied in binary combinations of cationic-cationic, cationic-nonionic and anionic-nonionic surfactant systems at 55°. The experimental results obtained from conductance and kinetic measurements allowed us to achieve significant information about the systems. Addition of cationic surfactant to nonionic surfactant accelerates the rate of hydrolysis. Kinetic data have been analysed by using Menger and Portnoy model. Binding constants and rate constants for the reaction in the micellar pseudo-phase, obtained from kinetic analysis, are also reported.

Mixed surfactant systems have received considerable interest both in theoretical and applied studies because of their technological and commercial applications. Mixtures of surfactants often exhibit synergism in their physicochemical properties, thus allowing particular applications. Often, the mixture may exhibit superior behaviour compared to the pure surfactant components. Many reports have been published in recent years dealing with solution properties of mixed surfactants containing ionic-nonionic, or mixed ionic micelles¹. However, there have been a very few studies analysing the influence of mixed surfactant systems on reaction processes². This prompted us to study alkaline hydrolysis of hydroxamic acid in mixed surfactant systems. The work reported here is part of a wider programme aimed at the understanding of the reaction mechanism in micellar solutions. For the last few years we have been studying the influence of cationic, anionic, zwitterionic and nonionic micelles in the acidic³ and alkaline⁴ hydrolysis of several

hydroxamic acids. Anionic micelles inhibit the reaction and cationic micelles accelerate hydrolysis. The rate surfactant profiles can be fitted quantitatively with regard to distribution of hydroxamic acids between micellar and aqueous phases. In this report we have employed binary combinations of cationic-cationic, cationic-nonionic, and anionic-nonionic surfactants. The systems that have been chosen for the alkaline hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) are presented in Table 1.

The ideal mixing theory has been quite successful in explaining the properties of surfactants having similar structures but can hardly account for the characteristics of mixed systems of dissimilar structural features. An attempt has also been made to determine the critical micellar concentrations of mixed micelle using electrical conductivity measurement.

Results and Discussion

The alkaline hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic

Table 1

Cationic/Cationic	Cationic/Nonionic	Anionic/Nonionic
CTAB	CTAB	SDS
I [C ₁₆ H ₃₃ N ⁺ (CH ₃) ₃ Br ⁻]	I [C ₁₆ H ₃₃ N ⁺ (CH ₃) ₃ Br ⁻]	I [C ₁₂ H ₂₅ OSO ₃ Na ⁺]
+	+	+
CPC	Brij-35	Brij-35
[C ₁₆ H ₃₃ N ⁺ C ₅ H ₅ Cl ⁻]	[C ₁₂ H ₂₅ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂₃ OH]	[C ₁₂ H ₂₅ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂₃ OH]
	and	
	CTAB	
	II [C ₁₆ H ₃₃ N ⁺ (CH ₃) ₃ Br ⁻]	
	+	
	TX-100	
	[C ₉ H ₁₉ C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) _{9.5} OH]	

acid is of the first order in both hydroxamic acid and hydroxide ion. The influence of cationic (CTAB), anionic (SDS) and nonionic (TX-100, and Brij-35) surfactants varying between 0 and $20.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ on the alkaline hydrolysis of PBHA, was studied at fixed concentration of NaOH (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) in 10% (v/v) dioxane at 55° . The addition of cationic surfactant (CTAB) increases the observed rate constant. Nonionic micelles have little-enhancing effect on reaction rate (Table 2). The addition of anionic surfactant decreases the hydrolysis rate. The kinetic data can be explained by means of the pseudophase model⁵ which treats micelles and water as separate reaction media. According to this model, profiles of k_{ψ} (the observed first order rate constant) vs surfactant concentration depend on substrate charge and hydrophobicity, surfactant head group charge, and counter ion concentration and type. Despite the successful kinetic treatments, our understanding of microenvironmental and orientational effects on both reactants and activated complex within the micelle is rather immature. It is usually assumed that solutes preferentially bind in the Stern layer of micelles of binding sites immersed in the aqueous environment. But the nature of these binding sites may vary with subtle changes in the solute. Orientational effects in the solute-micelle binding process, which will directly affect the directionality of a chemical reaction in the Stern layer, are largely a matter of ignorance. *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) has proved to be very hydrophobic substrate and tends to dissolve mainly into the micellar pseudophase. The cationic nature of the surfactant will favour the presence of OH^- in the micellar medium, accelerating the hydrolysis of the substrate associated with

the micelle. At higher concentration of surfactants, the acceleration effect is slow due to the increase of the concentration of counter ions (anions) which compete with OH^- . The inhibition of the reaction by anionic micelles could be rationalized in terms of proximity effects. In the anionic micelles, the substrates get incorporated hydrophobically and the anionic hydrolysing agent (OH^-) repelled electrostatically, thus separating the reactants from one another resulting in the observed inhibition.

The results of the alkaline hydrolysis of PBHA in the mixed micellar solutions are shown in Table 2. Although k_{ψ} is lesser than that of single cationic (CTAB) surfactant, in the case of nonionic and ionic surfactants the observed rate constant increases as the total surfactant concentration increases. When ionic and nonionic surfactants are mixed together to form mixed micelle, molecules of the nonionic surfactant penetrate between the molecules of ionic surfactant. This makes the surface charge density of the mixed micelle to be lower than that of the single ionic micelle, leading to the decrease of exclusion between ionic head groups of the ionic surfactant⁶ and the increase of the ion-dipole interaction between the ionic and the nonionic surfactants⁷. Thus molecules and ions of surfactants of different types in the mixed micelle interface are more open and more hydrated, and one would expect that k_m , the rate constant in the micellar pseudo-phase, should increase. The results indicate that mixed pseudo-phase should increase. The results also indicate that mixed micelles of ionic, non-ionic behave as ionic micelles. When the Stern layer becomes more compact in the mixed micelle, its water content decreases⁸ then it makes the polarity of the Stern layer

Table 2. Alkaline hydrolysis of *N*-penylbenzohydroxamic acid in mixed micellar system at 55°

Mixed System $\times 10^3$ [Surfactant]	$10^5 k_{\psi} (\text{s}^{-1})$							
	CTAB	Brij-35	TX-100	SDS	CTAB ^a + CPC	CTAB ^a + Brij-35	CTAB ^a + TX-100	SDS ^a + Brij-35
0.0	4.9	4.9	4.9	4.9	4.9	4.9	4.9	4.9
1.4	13.8	5.7	5.1	4.6	13.0	11.2	9.6	5.5
2.7	21.1	6.4	5.5	—	19.2	14.6	12.5	6.0
4.1	30.9	6.9	6.0	4.0	23.8	21.5	18.0	—
6.9	48.0	7.4	6.2	3.5	35.6	33.2	23.7	7.1
8.0	50.1	—	—	3.1	38.0	34.5	30.0	7.6
10.3	56.6	7.5	6.3	—	41.8	38.7	37.0	—
11.7	58.6	—	—	3.0	44.5	42.0	38.8	8.5
13.7	63.7	7.6	6.5	—	46.5	45.0	40.8	9.3
15.0	—	8.1	6.7	2.9	47.1	49.5	43.5	10.0
20.6	64.0	9.0	6.9	2.7	47.5	61.7	47.5	13.4

^aC mixed = $C_1 = C_2$; medium = 0.1 M NaOH and 10% (v/v) 1,4-dioxane.

decrease and alkaline hydrolysis of hydroxamic acid is slower in a lower polar situation. Furthermore, with the rising compactness of the Stern layer in the mixed micelle, its viscosity is higher than that of a single one, and it is more difficult for the substrate to make translation and rotation in the mixed micelle, so the increase of microviscosity⁹ will result in the decrease of reaction rate. The mixed micelles of CTAB and Brij-35 behave as ionic micelles. In the light of the non-ideal solution theory of Rubingh molecular interaction in the micelle is strongly attractive¹⁰. Addition of nonionic surfactants reduces counterionic concentrations at micellar surfaces and also dilutes reactants by increasing the volume of the micellar pseudophase¹¹. In general, it has been found that there is a stronger interaction between anionic/nonionic systems than between cation/nonionic mixtures¹².

The cmc of the mixed surfactants was determined by conductance measurement. The cmc of the mixed systems and pure surfactants are listed in Table 3. The mixed systems indicate regular behaviour in their properties.

Table 3. Values of k_m and K_s for the *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid

Surfactants	CMC $10^3 M$	k_m $10^5 (s^{-1})$	K_s	Correlation coefficient
CTAB	0.60	84.6	151.8	0.992
Brij-35	0.05	9.70	152.9	0.992
TX-100	0.028	7.86	105.9	0.961
SDS	1.00	1.55	122.4	0.982
CTAB + CPC (1 : 1)	0.71	51.0	295.9	0.984
CTAB + Brij-35 (1 : 1)	0.10	227.0	18.4	0.992
CTAB + TX-100 (1 : 1)	0.48	159.0	23.9	0.996
SDS + Brij-35 (1 : 1)	0.032	43.9	11.2	0.987

D_T Range = 1.4×10^{-3} to $20.6 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Quantitative treatment : Kinetic results have been explained by the pseudophase model (Menger and Portony model). According to this model (Scheme 1) the overall reaction rate constant (k_{Ψ}) will be the sum of the contributions of rate constants in water (k_w) and in the micelles (K_m), and will therefore depend on the distribution of reactants between the pseudophase and appropriate rate constants in the phase.

Scheme 1

The first order rate constants (k_{Ψ}) are given by equation (1), where, k_w and k_m are first order rate constants in the aqueous and micellar pseudophases respectively, K_s is the binding constant of the substrate to micellized surfactant whose concentration (D_n) is that of total surfactant less than that of monomer ($D_n = [D] - \text{cmc}$),

$$k_{\Psi} = \frac{k_w + k_m K_s [D_n]}{1 + K_s [D_n]} \quad (1)$$

The expression for k_{Ψ} in equation (1) can also be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{k_w - k_{\Psi}} = \frac{1}{k_w - k_m} + \frac{1}{k_w - k_m} \cdot \frac{1}{K_s ([D] - \text{cmc})} \quad (2)$$

A plot of the left-hand-side of equation (2) vs $(1/[D] - \text{cmc})$ allows the calculation of k_m and K_s . Treating the data in Table 2 with equation (2) we obtain k_m and K_s . The results are given in Table 3.

Experimental

N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by benzoylating freshly prepared *N*-phenylbenzohydroxylamine. The cationic surfactants cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, CTAB (Sigma) and cetylpyridinium chloride, CPC (Loba chemie), nonionic surfactants Brij-35 (Sigma) and Triton-X-100 (Loba chemie) and anionic surfactant sodium dodecyl sulfate, SDS (B.D.H.) and 1,4-dioxane, NaOH and anhydrous FeCl_3 (Qualigens, A.R.) were all used as such. Double-distilled water was used.

Kinetics were followed spectrophotometrically by measuring the concentration of the hydroxamic acid by the colour reaction with Fe^{3+} ions. Aliquots of the reaction mixture periodically removed from resulting solutions were diluted to 10 ml and their absorbance measured with a Systronics 108 spectrophotometer. Pseudo-first order rate constants were obtained with a standard deviation below 0.5%. Least-squares analysis was carried out on a WIPRO 386 computer under MS DOS.

The cmc of the mixed micellar systems was measured by the conductance method (with a Systronics 303 conductivity meter) from the plots of specific conductance against concentration.

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